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SOCIAL PEACE AND SOCIAL JUSTICE

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Abstract:

It is impossible to achieve social peace without social justice. Where there are injustices of any kind, the tenability of peace is low. Peace is not peace if it only guarantees the absence of war. A state or society can be free from war but still grapple with chaos and conflict because of the deep-seated injustices in the system. For example, besides the civil war of 1967-1970, Nigeria has witnessed a long season of negative peace that is laced with generations of agitations and protests especially from the disgruntled elements in the country as a result of systemic injustices. This paper discusses the complementarity of social peace and social justice – arguing primarily, that peace cannot reign anywhere without justice. And even if such a society exists, the best it has is negative peace, which is the absence of war.

Keywords: Social Peace; Social Justice; Positive Peace; Negative Peace.

Introduction

Every society, whether primitive or civilized, deeply desires peace. However, peace is neither an abstract concept nor an unattainable goal. Achieving social peace is possible, but it requires more than mere wishful thinking. It does not occur accidentally or spontaneously, nor is it a phenomenon limited to certain societies based on race, religion, or geography.

Social peace is essential for human interactions and cooperation, but it is not an isolated factor. It depends on several foundational elements, with social justice being a crucial pillar. Without justice, peace cannot exist. Social injustices lead to frustration, which can escalate into aggression and, if not addressed, can result in chaos. No state wishes for such disorder. Therefore, to prevent chaos, social justice must be integral to the fundamental structures of society. A society that seeks peace must prioritize uncompromised justice as its core foundation. Without this, peace becomes elusive, and various forms of violence and terror—a hallmark of a failed state—will prevail.

This article will explore the underlying principles of social peace and social justice, and how the latter supports the former.

Underlying Assumptions:

What is Social Peace?

The concept of social peace is complex and multifaceted, varying according to the perceptions, cultures, and worldviews of different societies. Despite the challenge of defining it universally, certain fundamental assumptions about social peace can be explored.

Social peace is a state where people in a society are free from war, psychological violence, cultural violence, structural violence, and any other threats, whether real or perceived, that could disrupt their peaceful existence. It is a collective benefit arising from collective responsibility, meaning that everyone in society contributes to and enjoys peace based on their efficient participation.

For instance, in a democratic society with three key branches of government—the Executive, Legislature, and Judiciary—all must work together and independently to maintain peace. If any of these branches fails or enacts measures that undermine peace, such as repressive laws or violations of rights, achieving social peace becomes difficult. It is crucial to distinguish social peace from individual peace. An individual, though part of society, may experience peace due to personal circumstances, while the majority may be denied peace due to societal structures.

For example, a wealthy person might secure personal safety in a dysfunctional society, while the poor majority cannot. Only in a state of war is individual peace impossible. Thus, social peace, or peace within a society, involves a situation where every member of the society:

1. Is included directly or indirectly in the governance of the society.
2. Is free from psychological violence.
3. Is free from real and perceived threats.
4. Is regularly involved in societal affairs.

5. Has access to societal resources and wealth.
6. Is content and not preoccupied with basic needs such as food, clothing, and shelter.

In such a situation, there is equal opportunity for all members to pursue happiness and contribute to the consolidation of peace. Social peace is a process requiring the collective effort of everyone in society. It is not spontaneous or accidental but a deliberate endeavor. Any serious society committed to achieving social peace must work hard collectively and patiently.

What is Social Justice?

Like many social terms, social justice lacks a universal definition and has been interpreted differently by various scholars in the field. Despite these diverse definitions, there is a consensus that social justice is fundamentally about "justice and fairness in society." This concept involves the principles that should govern the basic structure of a society, focusing on the equitable distribution of rights, opportunities, and resources among all individuals.

In this context, the following discussion will examine the underlying assumptions of social justice as presented by different scholars and authorities.

Investopedia defines social justice as the idea that all members of society deserve equal opportunities regarding education, political rights, and the distribution of wealth and privileges, enabling them to lead fulfilling lives and realize their potential within the community.¹ This implies that everyone should have equal access to education, the right to vote and be elected, create wealth, and participate in resource distribution to fulfill their purpose. Any deviation from this constitutes social injustice, where only the privileged, elite, and ruling class have access to quality education, good quality of life, lucrative employment opportunities, and commonwealth, perpetuating their power to the exclusion and detriment of the unprivileged majority.

¹ Investopedia. (n.d.). *Social justice*. Retrieved from <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/s/social-justice>

John Rawls, widely regarded as one of the most important political philosophers of the second half of the 20th century, conceptualizes justice as fairness. He envisions a society of free citizens holding equal basic rights and cooperating within an egalitarian economic system.² Rawls' stance on social justice emphasizes that everyone should have the opportunity to be free and possess equal basic rights, thereby allowing them to cooperate and live within an economic system that protects the interests of all, not just a select few.

From a Marxist perspective, social justice entails complete economic equality for all members of society. Marxists argue that wealth should be collected by the government and evenly distributed among everyone. They critique the economic structure of society, identifying it as the root cause of social injustice. They highlight the significant economic disparity between the rich and the poor and believe that the only way to resolve this inequality is through the equal redistribution of wealth, leading to a just society.³ Any deviation from this egalitarian distribution, according to Marxist theory, is considered social injustice.

The Catholic Agency for Justice, Peace and Development (CARITAS) defines social justice as promoting just societies and fair treatment of individuals and communities, based on the belief in innate human dignity.⁴ This perspective emphasizes that humans must be treated justly and fairly because of their inherent dignity. Regardless of race, tribe, background, economic class, sex, or religion, everyone must be treated with respect for their innate human dignity to establish social justice.

Despite the various interpretations of social justice, a common theme is its inclusivity and the avoidance of marginalizing anyone. Any deviation from the true meaning of social justice can disrupt social peace.

² Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy. (n.d.). *John Rawls*. Retrieved from <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/rawls/>

³ American Thinker. (2010, May). *What exactly is social justice?* Retrieved from https://www.americanthinker.com/articles/2010/05/what_exactly_is_social_justice.html

⁴ Caritas Aotearoa New Zealand. (n.d.). *What is social justice?* Retrieved from <https://www.caritas.org.nz/what-social-justice>

How Social Justice Promotes Social Peace

"Where justice is denied, where poverty is enforced,
where ignorance prevails, and where any one class is
made to feel that society is an organized conspiracy
to oppress, rob, and degrade them, neither persons
nor property will be safe." – Frederick Douglass⁵

This quotation clearly demonstrates that social peace can only be achieved through social justice. The absence of justice disrupts peace in society. With the concepts of social justice and social peace firmly established, we can explore how social justice promotes social peace.

Peace is highly desired, but it is neither free nor cheap. For any society to enjoy peace, a price must be paid, and in this context, the price is social justice. A society devoid of justice should prepare for the absence of peace. Without social justice, social peace is unattainable. For peace to exist, the following indicators of social justice must be embedded in the societal structure.

⁵ Extracted from Brainy Quote: BrainyQuote. (n.d.). *Quotes about social justice*. Retrieved from <https://www.brainyquote.com/quotes/keywords/>

First, there must be fairness. Everyone in society must be treated equitably, as outlined in the Constitution. No one should be above the law. The law must not favor a few while punishing the rest. Instead, it should ensure that those who break the law are punished accordingly, and those who deserve recognition are acknowledged as specified by the law. Fairness in line with the constitution will promote social peace if strictly followed.

For instance, in Saudi Arabia, there is relative social peace because of social justice. Although the law is strict and rigid, it applies to everyone, regardless of social status. Whether from the Royal Family or not, justice is fairly distributed, resulting in social peace. In 2016, The Institute for Environment and Human Security at the UN University named Saudi Arabia the third most safe and secure country.⁶ The Global Peace Index also ranked Saudi Arabia as the 133rd most peaceful country in the world. Furthermore, the top 10 countries on the Global Peace Index Ranking—such as Iceland, New Zealand, and Portugal—are all places where fairness, equity, and social justice prevail. These countries are peaceful because of their commitment to social justice.

Conversely, in Nigeria, peace is merely the absence of war. Fairness and equity are lacking in Nigerian society. The legal system is designed to oppress the poor and favor the ruling class. For example, if a top government official is guilty of corruption, the matter is often overlooked, and any punishment is not proportionate to the crime. On the other hand, a powerless individual who steals a small amount faces severe punishment. This unjust system prevents true peace.

⁶ Arab News. (2016, September 26). *Saudi Arabia ranks high in global peace index*. Retrieved from <https://www.arabnews.com/node/980251/saudi-arabia>

Second, the political process must be inclusive, allowing everyone to vote and be voted for, and the power structure must be just. It should not allow a particular group or tribe to dominate power. Before 1994 in South Africa, the power structure favored only Whites, leading to a long struggle for freedom by the Black population, culminating in 1994 but at great cost. A just political structure would have prevented such turmoil.

The Arab Spring in North Africa and the Middle East also exemplifies how unjust political structures can disrupt social peace. Leaders' attempts to perpetuate their power led to widespread unrest. Similarly, the 1993 election crisis in Nigeria showed how an unjust political structure can lead to violent protests and disrupt peace.

In contrast, countries like the USA, Finland, New Zealand, and Denmark, with just political structures and good governance, rarely experience disruptions in social peace. Any society with an unjust political structure will never know peace.

Third, there must be an equitable distribution of resources. Resources should benefit everyone, not just a select group. When a region or group is deprived, social peace is disrupted. For example, the Niger Delta region of Nigeria has seen various insurgent groups rise due to marginalization and poverty. The unjust economic structure, controlled by Northern political elites and their Southern allies, perpetuates this unrest. Unless there is a fair redistribution of wealth and resources, social peace will remain elusive.

Similarly, the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB) disrupt social peace with their protests against the unjust structure of Nigerian society. Equitable resource distribution, as seen in countries like Finland and Sweden, promotes relative peace.

Lastly, employment opportunities and the employment screening process must be just. Employment should be based on merit, not reserved for particular tribes or groups. During the Buhari administration⁷, allegedly, the Department of State Security in Nigeria secretly recruited primarily from the Fulani tribe, causing resentment and potential conflict. Admission to schools should also be based on merit, and all groups should be encouraged to pursue education. Societies where people are free to pursue happiness justly, like Norway, which topped the global happiness ranking in 2017, tend to be more peaceful.

Undoubtedly, social justice is integral to social peace. Fairness, inclusivity, equitable resource distribution, and just employment opportunities all contribute to a peaceful society. Any deviation from these principles disrupts social peace.

Conclusion

In essence, social justice is a fundamental component of social peace. Without social justice, a society will never experience positive peace, which is far superior to the mere absence of war, known as negative peace. It is important for a nation that seeks consistency in its development or growth trajectory to maintain a sustainable system that promotes positive peace. Peace is not peace until there is equity and fairness.

⁷ Buhari was a former president of Nigeria. His tenure was between 2015 and 2023.

References

Books

1. G. B., Shedrack. (2006). *Introduction to Peace and Conflict Studies in West Africa: A Reader*. Ibadan: Spectrum Books Limited.
2. Carter, N. (2007). *The Politics of the Environment: Ideas, Activism, Policy*. New York: Cambridge University Press.

Websites

1. Investopedia. (n.d.). *Social justice*. Retrieved from <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/s/social-justice>
2. Garrett, J. (n.d.). *John Rawls' mature theory of social justice*. Western Kentucky University. Retrieved from <https://people.wku.edu/jan.garret/ethics/matrawls.htm>
3. Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy. (n.d.). *John Rawls*. Retrieved from <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/rawls/>
4. American Thinker. (2010, May). *What exactly is social justice?* Retrieved from https://www.americanthinker.com/articles/2010/05/what_exactly_is_social_justice.html
5. Caritas Aotearoa New Zealand. (n.d.). *What is social justice?* Retrieved from <https://www.caritas.org.nz/what-social-justice>
6. BrainyQuote. (n.d.). *Quotes about social justice*. Retrieved from <https://www.brainyquote.com/quotes/keywords/>
7. Arab News. (2016, September 26). *Saudi Arabia ranks high in global peace index*. Retrieved from <https://www.arabnews.com/node/980251/saudi-arabia>
8. Wikipedia. (n.d.). *Global Peace Index*. Retrieved from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Global_Peace_Index
9. World Atlas. (n.d.). *The best governments in the world*. Retrieved from <https://www.worldatlas.com/articles/the-best-governments-in-the-world.html>
10. World Happiness Report. (2017). *Happiness rankings*. Retrieved from <http://worldhappiness.report/ed/2017>